

Communication from multiple approaches

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The challenges faced by Ecuador require a multi-faceted approach. Interventions to find solutions to the crises should consider instances of dialogue between the greatest number of people involved, which implies implementing participatory methodologies, so that the measures to be implemented are sustained, and do not involve impositions by technicians who know little about the territories.

It is necessary to initiate meetings, forums, or programmes to reach consensus, that is to say, to strengthen communication spaces so that more people can express their aspirations and difficulties, thus identifying common aspects to be addressed with the limited public resources.

In parallel, it will be necessary to establish public commitments to truth, sincerity and the responsible use of mass media and social networks. It is not a matter of imposing moral criteria, but of achieving the common good by complying with the constitutional and legal order approved by a majority in 2008.

The rules regulating communication state that priority should be given to educational, cultural and informative content, as well as quotas and expressions of diversity. However, neither the citizens nor the media companies, let alone the public media, abide by these rules. And although it is also true that in Ecuador there is no legislation on online media, this does not imply unrestricted freedom to promote disinformation and corruption.

Given the scenario described above, it is urgent to discover, test and support internal harmonisation processes that will lead the country to strengthen democracy and stop being described as a narco-state. Towards this goal, it is important to have new communication models that bring together the main and relevant aspects of each area of knowledge in order to massively involve Ecuadorians, both affected and victims, who need to speak out. Better coexistence begins with the understanding that comes from active listening.